

Complexes of Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with *p*-Acetamido Benzaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone

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Manuscript received 2 November 1979, accepted 22 December 1979

The complex compounds of nickel(II) and copper(II) with *p*-acetamido benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone ($\text{CH}_3 - \text{CO} - \text{NH} - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 - \text{CH} = \text{N} - \text{NH} - \text{CS} - \text{NH}_2$), (Abbreviated as *p* abts) of the type $(\text{ML}_2)\text{SO}_4$ and (ML_2) have been prepared and characterised. The structures of these complexes have been established on the basis of their elemental analysis, ir uv and magnetic moment values. The nickel(II)-complexes were found to be diamagnetic and square planar. The copper(II)-complexes were found to be paramagnetic and their structures contributed more towards the planar ones.

P-Acetamidobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone is a well known antitubercular drug. Crim and others¹ have shown recently the importance of the metal chelates against cancer. This attracted the author's attention to prepare the *p*-acetamidobenzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone complexes of nickel(II) and copper(II) of which uptill now there is no mention in literature. The complexes have been characterised and their structures have been established with a view to add something new to the medicinal science, which will show, on test, whether these have actually got any anti diseases activity.

Materials: $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E.M.), $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E.M.) and $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{OSN}_4$ were employed in the present work.

Ligand solution :

0.02(*M*) Solution of ligand either in ethyl alcohol or 0.1 (*M*) NaOH solution was used.

Standard solution :

0.04(*M*) solutions of Ni(II) and Cu(II) were made and reserved.

Complexes : $[\text{M}(\text{pabts})_2]\text{SO}_4$:

Each of Ni(II) and Cu(II) solutions, was treated with ethanolic solution of the ligand in 1:2 molar ratio. In actual practice, to 20 cc of each of 0.04 (*M*) Ni(II) and Cu(II) solutions, 40 cc of 0.02 (*M*) ethanolic solution of the ligand were added and heated on water bath for more than an hour. Yellow coloured crystalline complexes formed were filtered, washed and dried in air.

Analytical data :

Found : Ni, 9.33 ; C, 38.26 ; H, 3.80 ; S, 15.27 and N, 17.83 percent.

For $[\text{Ni}(\text{pabts})_2]\text{SO}_4$, Calculated : Ni, 9.36 ; C, 38.29 ; H, 3.82 ; S, 15.31 and N, 17.87 percent.

Found : Cu, 10.00 ; C, 37.93 ; H, 3.78 ; S, 15.15 and N, 17.70 percent.

For $[\text{Cu}(\text{pabts})_2]\text{SO}_4$, Calculated : Cu, 10.05 ; C, 38.00 ; H, 3.80 ; S, 15.20 and N, 17.73 percent.

$\text{M}(\text{pabts})_2$: 30 cc of each of 0.04 (*M*) Ni(II) and Cu(II) solutions were treated in cold with a slight excess of 0.02 (*M*) ligand solution in 0.1(*M*) NaOH. Greenish yellow precipitate of $\text{Ni}(\text{pabts})_2$ was formed at pH 7-10. The complexes were allowed to settle for 15-20 minutes, filtered and then dried in air or in oven at 105-110°

Analytical data :

Found : Ni, 11.08 ; C, 45.26 ; H, 4.14 ; S, 12.06 and N, 21.12 percent.

For $[\text{Ni}(\text{pabts})_2]$, Calculated : Ni, 11.10 ; C, 45.39 ; H, 4.16 ; S, 12.10 and N, 21.18 percent.

Found : Cu, 10.00 ; C, 37.93 ; H, 3.78 ; S, 15.15 and N, 17.70 percent.

For $[\text{Cu}(\text{pabts})_2]$, Calculated : Cu, 10.06 ; C, 38.00 ; H, 3.80 ; S, 15.20 and N, 17.73 percent.

Results and Discussion

$[\text{M}(\text{pabts})_2]\text{SO}_4$ type of complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II) were yellow in colour. These were found to be soluble in acetone and carbon tetrachloride. The complexes were stable upto 140°. *Bis*-chelate complex of the type $[\text{Cu}(\text{pabts})_2]$ of Cu(II) appeared green

while similar bis-chelate of Ni(II) was found yellowish green. These were also soluble in methanol, acetone and carbon disulphide.

Magnetic moment : Magnetic moment, $\mu_{eff} = 0$ for both of the nickel(II) complexes showed them to be diamagnetic and square planar, involving dsp^2 hybridisations. $\mu_{eff} = 1.91$ BM for $[Cu(pabts)_2]SO_4$ and $\mu_{eff} = 1.90$ BM for $[Cu(pabts)_2]$ suggested them to be paramagnetic. The contribution to paramagnetism in each complex was more than one unpaired electron spin equivalent but less than two. The discrepancy may be explained due to orbital contribution and distortion of octahedral structures to square planar ones, leading to dsp^2 hybridisation. No exact information regarding geometry of the Cu(II) complexes can be obtained.

$[M(pabts)_2]SO_4$ complexes:

The Ni(II) complex was found to be spin paired type. Excitation² of one electron from $1A_{1g}$ ground term leads to $1B_{1g}$ term. The bands at $440 m\mu$ and $410 m\mu$ in the spectrum of Ni(II)-complex have been assigned due to $(1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1B_{1g})$ transition. The band at $330 m\mu$ has been assigned to the charge transfer band. The band due to $570 m\mu$ accounts for the yellow colour of the Ni(II) complex. The band at $510 m\mu$ may be probably due to slight contribution to $(1A_{1g} \rightarrow 3B_{1g})$ transition. These suggested the planar geometry of the Ni(II)-complex.

In the spectrum of the Cu(II) complex, the bands at $660 m\mu$ was assigned to $(2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2A_{1g})$ transition. Moreover, the band at $565 m\mu$ was attributed to $(2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g)$ transition. The band positions suggested the co-planar nature of the Cu(II)-complex. Out of the weak bands at 480 and $260 m\mu$, the latter has been accounted due to the charge transfer.

TABLE 1—U.V. SPECTRA

Complexes	λ max (m μ)
$[Ni(pabts)_2]SO_4$	570,510,410,330
$Ni(pabts)_2$	520,440,320,260
$[Cu(pabts)_2]SO_4$	660,565,480,260
$Cu(pabts)_2$	650,505,380 -

$M(pabts)_2$ complexes : The bands at 440 and $520 m\mu$ in the spectrum of the Ni(II)-chelates were assigned due to $(1A_{1g} \rightarrow 1B_{1g})$ and $(1A_{1g} \rightarrow 3B_{1g})$ transitions. Moreover, the bands due to charge transfer were observed at 320 and $260 m\mu$ in the spectrum of the Ni(II)-chelate. On the spin pair assumption of d^8 electrons in Ni led to $b_{2g}^2, e_g^4, a_{1g}^2 (S=O)$ which suggested the square planar structure of the complex.

TABLE 2—I.R. SPECTRA

$pabts$ cm ⁻¹	$[Ni(pabts)_2]SO_4$ cm ⁻¹	$Ni(pabts)_2$ cm ⁻¹	$Cu(pabts)_2SO_4$ cm ⁻¹	$Cu(pabts)_2$ cm ⁻¹	
3465 bs 3380	3460 bw 3380	3450 bw 3370	3410 bw 3390	3415 bw 3385	$\nu(NH)$ Co-NH-
3090 w 2875 2 1670 ms	3085 w 2870 w 1660 w	- 2870 w 1655 w	3080 w 2880 w 1665 w	- 2880 w 1660 w	- =CH-str. $\nu(C=O), NH$ or NH_2 bend
1645 s 1630 s	1635 ws 1620 w	1630 s 1620 ws	1640 vs 1625 ws	1635 vs 1625 vs	Sym C=N str. Asym C=N or NH
1525 w 1380 ms	1510 w 1380 ws	1530 w 1380 w	1535 ws 1390 ms	1535 s 1385 ms	$\delta(NH_2) + \nu(CN)$ $CH_3-CO, Sym-CH_3$
1350 s	1320 ms	-	1330 s	-	$\nu(C=s), N-C-N$ $\nu(C-N)$ or $C-NH_2$
-	1100-30vs	-	1100-35vs	-	SO ₄ -2
-	-	1025 w 910 bw	-	1000 bw 905 bw	Ring Substitution N-C=N or $\nu(C-SH)$
860 b	8606	860 w	860 w	860 w	Paradisubstituted ring
-	-	765 w	-	775 w	$\nu(C-S)$
-	530 s	520 s	480 bs	490 bs	$\nu(M-N)$
-	525 ws	450 ws	435 ws	430bs	$\nu(M-S)$
-	570 ws	-	455 ₃ ws	-	$\nu(M-N) + \nu(M-S)$

In the spectrum of the Cu(II)-chelate, the bands at 650 and 505 $m\mu$ were assigned to ($2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2A_{1g}$) and ($2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$) transitions respectively. These bands were found to be slightly polarised. The band at 380 $m\mu$ was very weak. The positions of the bands suggested the square planar geometry of the Cu(II)-chelate. The band at 505 $m\mu$ also explained the green colour of the complex.

Infrared Spectra :

I. R. spectra of the ligand and complexes were studied between 4000-200 cm^{-1} using KBr matrices and the results were placed in Table 2.

$[M(pabts)_2]SO_4$ complexes :

The band due to $\nu(C=S)$ at 1350 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand has been shifted downwards at 1320 and 1330 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes. This observation is supported by the earlier measurement by Pandey³, who found $\nu(C=S)$ at 1300-20 cm^{-1} in the Cr(II)-complexes of the substituted benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone. The decrease in frequency, without making any considerable modification of intensity suggested the coordination to Ni(II) or Cu(II) through sulphur atom of the C=S group.

The band at 1645 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand due to $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$ and NH of hydrazine residue of the ligand decreased to 1635 and 1640 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes. This further suggested the coordination to Ni(II) or Cu(II) through nitrogen atom of $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ i.e., Schiff's base residue of the ligand. On complexation, a slight increase in intensity for Cu(II)-complex has been noted.

The coordination to metal atom through N of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ of the Schiff's base residue has been supported by Pandey³ and Pradhan⁴.

The sharp band at 1630 cm^{-1} was assigned to asymmetrical $\text{C}=\text{N}$ frequency, which shifted to the lower frequencies i.e., at 1620 and 1625 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes. The decrease in intensity in case of Ni(II)-complex was attributed to the complex formation. Sahni and others⁵ found sym ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) and asym ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) frequencies in the dibenzylidene dipicolonic acid complexes at 1640 and 1630 cm^{-1} .

$\nu(\text{CN}) + \delta(\text{NH}_2)$ -Vibration frequency has been observed at 1525 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand. But that shifted upwards at 1530 and 1535 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes. Increase in frequency on complex formation has also been reported by the earlier workers⁴⁻⁶.

Broad sharp bands at 1100-30 and 1100-35 in the spectra of the Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes indicated clearly that the sulphate groups are ionic and existed in the complexes, out side the coordination spheres.

Some new bands which appeared at low frequencies in the spectra of the complexes were probably

due to metal-nitrogen and metal-sulphur bond vibration frequencies. The sharp bands at 530 and 480 were assigned to $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{N})$ frequencies. The bands at 525 and 435 may be attributed to $\nu(\text{Ni}-\text{S})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu}-\text{S})$ frequencies respectively.

On the basis of the above evidences, it is obvious that the ligand 'pabts' is bidentate in nature and the complexes can be represented by the following structure.

Where $M = \text{Ni(II)}$ and Cu(II)

$M(pabts)_2$ complexes :

In an alkaline medium, i.e., at increased pH values H atom of NH_2 of the ligand contributes much to S than to N atom. Thus a tautomeric effect causes the ligand to undergo the thioenolic form, in which the double bond character of ($\text{C}=\text{S}$) decreases to ($\text{C}-\text{S}$) one, which is only possible after formation of $\text{C}-\text{SH}$ group i.e., thioenolic group. In this case, replacement of proton(H^+) form the acidic SH group and donation through N atom of Schiff's base residue become the potential affairs. The deprotonation at high pH values has been claimed in several cases. The bands at 1025 and 1000 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Ni(II) and Cu(II) respectively may be probably due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{SH})$ frequencies. Srivastva and others⁷ suggested $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ at (1010+10) and 990 cm^{-1} in tripropyltin dithiocarbamate. Moreover, the replacement of H of SH group of the thioenolic ligand has been confirmed by the presence of clear bands due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ at 765 and 775 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes. Murthy and others⁸ suggested $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ at 720 and 727 cm^{-1} for Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes.

(Thioenolic form)

Mohapatra and others⁹ suggested $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ at 1235 cm^{-1} Ghosh and others¹⁰ suggested $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ in thiocyanate complexes of Pt group metals at 690-756 cm^{-1} . Thus $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ or $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ frequency varies largely from one to another complexes.

$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ which was found in the spectrum of the ligand at 1645 cm^{-1} , decreased and modified intensity at 1630 and 1635 cm^{-1} in the spectra of Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes. This clearly showed the coordination through nitrogen atom of $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ (Schiff's base residue).

Low frequency bands at 520 and 490 cm^{-1} were assigned to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$, which is supported by the author's earlier work¹¹ for identical ligand site. The

bands at 450 and 430 cm^{-1} may be probably due to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ in the Ni(II) and Cu(II)-complexes respectively.

Mohapatra⁹ assigned $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{S})$, at 260 cm^{-1} . Srivastva⁷ found $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{S})$ at 370 cm^{-1} . Udupa¹² showed Mo-S at 470 cm^{-1} in the thiosalts. The very low frequency of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ may be probably due to increased dimension of sulphur atom.

Thus the structures of the chelate complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II) can be represented as follows :—

Where $\text{M}=\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dr. Satya P. Popli, Medicinal Deptt., C.D.I.R, Lucknow, who helped in recording the various spectral data and also to Dr. L. K. Mishra, Patna Science College, who provided instrument for magnetic study. The author is sincerely

thankful to Dr. Y. Thakur, Head of Chemistry Dept., Mithila University, Darbhanga who helped in study of various analyses and gave valuable suggestions.

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